

Difficulty Adjustment and the Augmented State Space of Mining Equilibrium Models

Craig S. Wright

University of Exeter, Exeter, United Kingdom

Email: cw881@exeter.ac.uk

ORCID: 0000-0001-9374-0507

Abstract

Difficulty adjustment in proof-of-work blockchains creates a common state variable in mining payoffs that is absent from the homogeneous-Poisson identification used in much of the equilibrium-modelling literature. This paper characterises the omission and shows that its leading effect on aggregate mining counts is the opposite of what a homogeneous-Poisson model assumes. Conditional exponentiality of block arrivals survives within an adjustment epoch, but the protocol's periodic re-targeting precludes exact homogeneous-Poisson representation across epoch boundaries (Theorem 4.3; Proposition 4.7). Because each epoch contains exactly K blocks and the difficulty re-targeting makes epoch durations a first difference of a stationary sequence, the cumulative calendar-time block count grows in variance far more slowly than the homogeneous-Poisson benchmark: $\text{Var}(N(T)) = \kappa_0 K + \kappa_1 n_T + o(K + n_T)$ with $\kappa_0, \kappa_1 = \Theta(1)$, so the variance grows linearly in the horizon but with a per-epoch slope of order one against the homogeneous-Poisson per-epoch variance K , and the dispersion ratio $\text{Var}(N(T))/\mathbb{E}[N(T)] \rightarrow \kappa_1/K = \Theta(1/K)$, far below the homogeneous-Poisson value of one (Theorem 4.9; full proof in Section OA-3 of the Online Appendix). Conditional on the strongly under-dispersed aggregate (dispersion ratio $\Theta(1/K)$), individual miners' counts are binomial—smaller than the Poisson prediction by the factor $(1 - q_i)$ —and distinct miners' counts are negatively correlated, tending to perfect negative correlation in the two-symmetric-miner case (and to $-1/(m - 1)$ for m equal miners). The protocol is therefore variance-reducing for the aggregate calendar-time count relative to the homogeneous-Poisson benchmark—not for the within-epoch flow rate, and not for the dominant empirical risks of mining: the canonical identification implies larger cumulative count risk than the augmented-state specification for risk-averse miners. The second-order stochastic dominance of pool over solo mining (Cong et al. 2021) is preserved and quantitatively strengthened (Corollary 4.10). The qualitative conclusions of the engaged equilibrium-modelling papers survive; we develop one central application—the mining-pool risk-sharing model of Cong et al. (2021)—in full and provide mapping implications, not theorem-level corrections, for the remaining engaged papers, with the within-epoch flow-rate channel rather than the cumulative-count channel carrying the surviving state dependence.

Keywords: blockchain, proof-of-work, memoryless approximation, difficulty adjustment, mining equilibrium, Poisson process, augmented state.

JEL codes: C73, D47, G29, L86.

Data availability. The complete replication package—the Monte Carlo source code, fixed seeds, output schema, SHA-256 hashes, and the Bitcoin difficulty calibration data—is archived at Zenodo, DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20320253>.

Disclosure. Anthropic's Claude was used for literature search. All other work was performed by the author.